

Geographical Indication Legal Protection Efforts of Non-Rattan Wood Forest Products as Indonesia's Natural Wealth

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Protection law, Fairness Geographical Indication, Geographical</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5167695</p>	<p><i>This study discusses the potential protection of Geographical Indication (GI) towards natural resources as the national or state assets, the right of the local community to the economic or commercial values of the geography from their region. Analyzing federal laws and international legal agreements related to the Geographical Indication that adopts the fairness concept approach emphasizes fairness, equal opportunity, and reciprocity. Currently, GI protection has discriminated in terms of the safety of GI merely protects agriculture resources oar yields, processed products, handmade or other natural resources products. The product is related more to mark. Nevertheless, GI is only associated with geography characteristics, qualities and reputations and local community of all-natural resources, i.e. rattan as the state assets which should be protected. This study finds that fairness demands Geographical Indication protection law that gives optimal protection to national assets, equal justice, and provides Indication to the area with high economic and community.</i></p>

Introduction

Today, Indonesia is faced with a unique legal performance problem regarding the formal truth of being treated as the most dominant consideration of legal decision making. An approach that can be used is still in the further discussion through a more holistic alternative paradigm (Sutrisno, 2015). Special lawful handling is needed, for that social problem must be handled extraordinarily by law and must also work in an extraordinary way (Sutrisno, 2014). This condition is the most fundamental reason for formulating the policy so that this law is made (Sutrisno, 2019). According to Radbruch, three fundamental values must be realized if the law wants to get the executor's attention, such as the value of certainty, justice and benefit (Alexy, 2006). Warassih provides a further explanation (Warassih, 2011), that these three fundamental values will direct the law to consider the needs of society at a particular time so that The law does have an essential role (function) (goal) for the organization. Law enters all aspects of human life, mainly providing a framework for the relationships that members of society make with each other that are social to change policies in their implementation.

The export ban on rattan is regulated in the Regulation of the Trade Minister of the Republic of Indonesia No.35 of 2011 concerning Rattan Export Provisions. However, the smuggling of rattan by domestic and foreign actors is still happening, and there is no deterrent effect. Ironically, rattan is purchased by competing countries for the rattan industry, making their products compete with Indonesian rattan products. The rattan community feels that this law no longer gives a sense of certainty, benefit and justice. As expected. Most of the rattan is exported to competing countries that produce rattan furniture and handicraft products. Price wars with competing countries impact the rattan market outside of being more dominated by them. The sense of injustice does not stop there because the rattan is owned illegally. Therefore, when the rattan is used by competing countries and claimed as their product, it is unfair. What they should be able to produce in Indonesia, and the certificate of origin should be Indonesia. Indonesia has the freedom to claim it as its property because it is rattan which geographically does not originate or grow in their country, and they always need rattan from Indonesia. Rattan - rattan, which geographically creates or is legally owned by Indonesia, should have the right to profit or ownership over any product made from Indonesian rattan. Suppose other countries, without seeing their position as developed countries, but their place in Indonesia. In that case, they will undoubtedly do the same to get justice and prevent unfair competition.

Rattan in Indonesia has different qualities and characteristics depending on the region or geographic origin. The reputation of Indonesian rattan is other because of the nature of where it comes from, the geographical origin of the forest, and this is the economic value of Indonesian rattan. The economic value attached to this rattan belongs to the Indonesian people because this rattan comes from the earth / geographical Indonesia. Economic values such as the characteristics, quality and reputation of Indonesian rattan make it able to compete. Ownership rights should be preserved and not allowed to be stolen or belong to other countries, especially it will kill the Indonesian rattan industry. Moreover, there is already a law that prohibits the export of rattan, but rattan

can still be smuggled into use by competing countries. The law on the prohibition of exports is a moral guideline for the state and the Indonesian people.

The high economic value attached to rattan because geographically is an asset of Indonesia and has global business opportunities has been stolen continuously by other countries. This is because no law functions with certainty and specifically, which protects an area with a geographical location with high economic value. This superior geography has resulted in rattan and other natural resources with good characteristics, quality and reputation. Therefore, they continue to buy more and more, even though competing countries illegally buy them. Because rattan from Indonesia is well known to various countries in the European world, America and others have advantages in the furniture industry. The superiority of Indonesian rattan due to its geographic excellence and tropical climate should naturally receive the same protection by the Geographical Indication (GI) Protection Law. The Government should fight for this right for the sake of justice for the rattan community and honour for Indonesia if its geographical reputation is recognized. Indonesia is entitled to equal opportunity rights and legal protection to be recognized as a geographical reputation that has produced superior products and has a high economy. Immanuel Kant argued that the law and the state protect the human rights of its citizens (Arinanto and Triyanti, 2012).

The development of norms protecting regional names (geographic location) as a sign of recognizing the quality or characteristics of specific products initially due to brand protection became an important issue after being definitively introduced to international trade rules. The safety of the geographic indication system internationally is regulated in the WTO framework, particularly the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPs) (Sarac, 2015).

Because the difference in quality has a critical trade value that must be protected by law, which is universal because grapes are grown in various countries with different geographies, this law aims to prevent counterfeiting, fraud, and unfair competition. The regulations stipulated by the WTO must be obeyed by all countries that sign the world trade agreement, which must ratify it in the national law in each country.

In Article 22 (1), the TRIPs agreement states that geographical indications are, for this Agreement, indications which identify a good as originating in the territory of a Member, or a region or locality in that territory, where a given quality, reputation or another characteristic of the good is essentially attributable to its geographical origin (Panel Reports, 2020). The Law on Geographical Indications Protection prioritizes the validity of geographic origins in terms of materials or other matters related to geographies such as characteristics, qualities that make products have economic value to prevent product counterfeiting and unfair competition (Sitepu, 2018). How about products from other countries, but the origin of materials is geographically from Indonesia. It is made in their country. The Geographical Indication of its arrangement in the TRIPs Agreement does not further regulate certain norms that the participating States must follow. The minimum standard that each participating country must carry out is only to carry out legal methods in the framework of protection (lawful means), including unfair competition. Geographical Indication Rules may be included inside or outside the Mark rules.

The limited benefits of Geographical Indications Protection to the origin associated with brands do not provide fair justice. Because there are neglected rights, that is, the protection of geographical indications regarding the validity of geographic origins, so it does not depend on brands. Geographical Indication Norms are related to natural products such as grapes as well as rattan. Natural resources should not only be limited to agriculture, etc., as regulated by world covenants. But what is called the result of geography is all, when goods have been made or processed into new consumer products, they are called goods and can be given a brand to obtain special rights to the Brand. But geographic rights are separate.

The Law on Geographical Indications Protection in Indonesia is regulated in Law No.20 of 2016. Its implementation is handled in Government Regulation No.51 of 2007; it must be explored whether it has provided justice and the appropriate benefits for the Indonesian people. But can it be said that it is fair when the Geographical Indication Protection law is related to the ownership of a product related to a brand rather than identifying the geographical origin or the validity of the geographical origin?

The law regulating the country of origin is the Certificate of Origin (COO) determined by the WTO or the certificate of goods origin regulated. The Minister of Trade Regulation No. 43/M-DAG-PER/10/2007 should be able to be used as supporting legality, even if only as a description of the origin of goods which the GI does not regulate. The COO is essential to determine the country of origin first. Only then did IG set geographic origins. So the COO is the legality that determines that any asset from any country can be transferred to the right of control of goods so that there is no illegal trading. How is the implementation of Geographical Indication Legal Protection optimal to provide adequate protection, and how our efforts to optimize the Geographical Indication legal Protection to protect rattan?

Method

This research uses normative legal investigation, which is a type of legal research obtained from literature studies, analyzing legal issues of rattan export related to the protection of geographical indications. The research approach is the conceptual approach (conceptual approach) and legislation (statue approach).

Results and Discussion

For Robert Nozick, justice only emerges or is better associated with the context of the state. The role of the state, according to Roberts and Reich, is to protect individual rights, and nothing should be sacrificed for this purpose (Roberts and Reich, 2011). In addition, the state must cling to the principle of compensation (compensating) for those who have lost their rights and freedoms. As with Indonesian rattan, which is used to produce products from other countries, the state at least claims collective rights (Arinanto and Triyanti, 2012). Legal protection, which is more important for the weaker or less fortunate, is found in the thinking of Grotius, Thomas Hobbes, Spinoza, John Locke, and also John Rawls. Grotius said that the law exists because of an agreement or contract that occurs because humans are social creatures who desire to live in society. Law and the state aim to regulate society to be orderly and safe. If you want justice, there must be regulations governing it. Therefore a form is needed.

Strictly speaking, the concept of legal protection is an effort to protect someone's interests by allocating a human right power to them to act in the framework of their interests (Rahardjo, 2003). The law protects a person's interests by distributing power to them to work in their interests in a measured manner (Rahardjo, 2003). Interests are the target of rights because rights contain elements of protection and recognition. So, legal protection is constructed as a form of service and a protected subject (Salim and Nurbaini, 2013).

Geographical indications in international agreements are associated with other intellectual property rights such as industry, brands. Geographical Indication is meant as a sign or mark of goods registered related to e-Intellectual Property Rights about goods/product brands (Sitepu, 2018). It is used as an origin mark attached to the quality/characteristics of the goods. The use of signs as geographic indications can be in the form of tags or labels placed on the goods produced. The character can be the name of a place, region, word, picture, letter, or a combination of these elements. Protection of geographic indications includes goods produced by nature, agricultural goods, handicraft products; or other industrial products.

The law that regulates the export ban on raw materials already exists, such as the export ban on natural, raw rattan, semi-finished rattan ex HS 1401.20. Which is currently a prohibited commodity for export following the Regulation of the Minister of Trade Number: 35 / M-DAG / PER / 11/2011 banning the export of rattan in its complete form or without being processed is regulated in the Regulation of the Minister of Trade No. 44 / M-DAG / PER / 7/2012. The ban on the export of semi-finished rattan is held in the Regulation of the Minister of Trade (Permendag) No 5/2012. The smuggling is charged under Law No. 17 of 2006, in Article 102 A letter (a) concerning Customs. Regulation of the Minister of Trade No.36 of 2011 regulates the transportation of rattan between islands to prevent rattan smuggling. Meanwhile, Regulation of Trade No.37 of 2011 governs rattan in the warehouse receipt system.

Law as a system of norms in its development is used to regulate and maintain existing behavior patterns. Law is also needed to realize state policy in the social, cultural, economic, political, defense and national security fields (Warassih, 2011). The law serves community members in allocating power, distributing resources, protecting the interests of community members, and ensuring the achievement of goals set in society (Pitegoff, 2017). Rattan players in Indonesia deeply feel this unhealthy competition because the rattan used by competing countries, especially China, originates from the geographic trafficking of Indonesia, not legal. Ironically, it seems that the state is doing nothing.

Battle Competition in the market for rattan products is caused by "price wars". The rattan product exporters from Indonesia are getting smaller profits because domestic costs never go down but always go up. This makes local rattan product exporters or factories unable to raise prices for rattan artisans. As a result, it has become increasingly challenging to run a business in the rattan sector and has become sluggish. Many factories are closed because they are no longer profitable due to decreasing orders. After all, buyers who choose prices prefer to buy from competing countries, that is China, in addition to prices that are no longer competitive.

The Indonesian Government is expected to reform the law on the ban on rattan exports. So that the illegal export of rattan can be stopped, they were assessing policies that can be useful for protecting state assets such as rattan being stolen from other countries. So those Indonesian assets can be saved and used for the prosperity of the Indonesian people. Natural resources that are of economic value because of their geographic origin have characteristics, quality, and reputation supporting these economic values.

Due to the advantage of geographical environmental factors, Indonesian rattan can provide quality, characteristics, and reputation that are different from other countries. It has an economic value that can be bartered with technology from developed countries that do not have rattan or rattan other natural resources such

as Indonesia. So, rattan and other natural resources prohibited from being exported if they get the Geographical Protection law are expected to be no longer stolen but only produced in Indonesia. Property rights can be arranged together to provide benefits to all parties, especially for the community's welfare from the geographical area from which the goods are produced.

Thus, the value of Indonesia's natural resources can be equated with technology because technology without raw materials will not produce any useless product and vice versa. This is what is meant by justice in the sense of fairness that has been previously explained. Fairness or propriety, which is intended as a principle of reciprocity or mutual benefit. It does not only provide opportunities for people who have the intellect or ability or technology to enjoy various social benefits, but these advantages provide opportunities for those who are less fortunate, that is, the local community. The principle of reciprocity is also regulated in Article II GATT 1947, which requires reciprocal treatment between WTO member countries in international trade policies.¹⁴

The Geographical Identification Law (GI) in Indonesia must indeed be reexamined, primarily because it depicts natural resources because they are not products. This means that this law does not provide equality, which according to Rawls's principle quoted in the introduction, is unfair. Isn't it the GI law protected by geographic origins that have given the product a typical value?

What about rattan, categorized as not a protected product because it does not preserve its origin. Even though it has the characteristics, quality and reputation of geographic origin as meant by norms regulated in GI law. Therefore, it is illegally owned by other countries, and the products are claimed to belong to other countries because they are not produced in Indonesia. Can it be said that it is fair, even though the one who has the right should be Indonesia because the rattan originates from Indonesian Geographic?

The Law on Geographical Indications in Indonesia must protect areas and communities with geographic, economic, or cultural values. Because the characteristics, quality, and reputation come from geographic origins that give natural resources or products with monetary value, which can then be processed and branded and claimed jointly with the community, based on the geographical position of origin. By providing fair and equitable opportunities to local communities because geographically, they are rightfully called the priority rights owners, but now distributed to producers who process their natural resources into branded products.

In-Law No. 20 of 2016, Article 1 Paragraph (6), a definite indication is defined as a sign indicating the area of origin of an item showing the location of an item and product due to geographical, environmental factors, including natural factors, human factors or a combination. These two factors give particular reputation, quality and characteristics to the goods and products produced. No rule says GI should be included in a brand. TRIPs itself acknowledges that Brand and GI are independent regimes. The definition of the TRIPs Agreement regarding GI is outlined in Article 22 paragraph (1), as follows the Indication which identifies a good as originating in the territory of a member or a region or locality in that territory, where a given quality, representation or other characteristics of the goods is essentially attributable to its geographical origin. Based on the formulation of Article 22 paragraph (1) of the TRIPs Agreement, it is clear that geographical indications are to identify an area of a member country, or a place within the territory of the Member State, which indicates the origin of an item, which gives particular reputation, quality and characteristics of the goods. Concerned. In other words, the identity of an object can also be determined by geographic factors that indicate the existence of particular reputation, quality, and characteristics used as attributes of the goods concerned.

What form of protection is given to each country? There is hope that the Indonesian Government proposes geographic safety for geographic areas with characteristics, quality and reputation. That provides economic value to natural resources or products. They have commercial value and the ability to compete and incorporate natural resources or natural resources, which are state assets such as rattan which are essential and can prosper the local community. Apart from protecting geographic values that have economic value, there are also fundamental rights given to local communities because nature belongs to them. By getting the opportunity to get a fair profit, people voluntarily carry out the obligation to protect natural resources or assets in their area. And also support processing into products or provide added value to be given a marketable brand and compete freely, competitively nationally and internationally. Apart from using Law No.20 of 2016, the legal umbrella regarding geographical indications is regulated through Government Regulation No.51 of 2007 concerning Geographical Indications. Government Regulation No.51 of 2007 about Geographical Indications is implementing Law No. 20 of 2016. No article regulates the prohibition of unfair competition explicitly due to the misuse of geographical indications, even though this is one of these critical issues related to justice. As previously stated, the rattan used by other countries' claimed ownership is also a significant competitor in the rattan industry.

Rattan or other significant natural resources with commercial value due to geographical origins get a fair chance to be protected by GI law. Unfair competition due to unclear geographical origins or falsification of natural resources or products or stems must be precisely regulated to avoid the dishonest fraud that often occurs in trading nationally and internationally. To face world trade conventions in this era of globalization, the Indonesian Government must better understand the fairness concept of fairness, which emphasizes the principle of reciprocity or mutual benefit. Provide a fair opportunity or fair equality of opportunity to natural resources evenly because they have economic value due to good geographical characteristics to protect.

The Government is obliged to adopt the Fifth Principle of Pancasila to create a just and prosperous society in the implementation of state life. The principle of social justice has provided a way to give rights and obligations and society's primary institutions and determine the distribution of benefits and the burden of social cooperation appropriately.

Protection of Geographical Indications (GI) so that the registration of Indonesian assets is for Indonesia. If a foreign country wants to own, it must give its rights to the people from which the product comes; this is what is said to be fair (Mayasari, 2020). In a logical sense, products that contain IG are owned by the community which are directly related to the GI. However, within the legal protection framework, the party represents the community that holds the GI or the owner's society, who must actively register to claim ownership. The community of owners as interested parties can be carried out by representatives of the community or the local Government. The most important thing that must be considered for the protection of GI is the consistency of the quality of the regional characteristics of the product concerned. Either from nature, humans or a combination of both. Indonesia's participation in international conventions related to IPRs needs to be explored to strengthen the ownership of GI in a global, not only national, forum. So, with the protection of Geographical Indications, it is hoped that it will become a form of protection for the nation's assets and become a source of foreign exchange. Through a good and effective Geographical Indication protection system, it is hoped that the production potential through the Brand can be developed and utilized.

To harmonize all laws and regulations in the Field of Mark and GI with the TRIPS Approval, Law No. 20/2016 on Trademarks and Geographical Indications, implementing regulations still use Government Regulation No.15 of 2007. The word GI is used to identify the characteristics, quality, and reputation of an area where products or goods are made or produced or grown or produced. Then the goods produced will be given a brand which will then be registered so that their ownership can be claimed before being marketed to consumers. Protection of GI when it is addressed to areas which, because of its geography, have provided characteristics, quality, and reputation, such as the use of marks as a geographical indication in the form of a more precise label. Then this label is applied to the goods produced or produced, which will be branded to register ownership of the goods. So geographic identification protection is ultimately separated from the Brand. However, the placement must be arranged so that the request can be split. Protection of Geographical Identification of ownership due to characteristics, quality and reputation are given to where the goods are produced and will continue to be attached to the area (Mayasari, 2020). Its right is naturally given to the site and owned by the community in the area. Then it can be shared/used on goods or products produced by giving collective rights, which all local communities can enjoy. Thus, collective rights deserve to be given to the community from which the goods or products originate.

The Trademark and Geographical Protection Law need to be explored again to protect areas that have given the characteristics, quality and reputation of the products or goods produced that have economic value and the ability to compete or competitive advantage (Montrm, 2006). So that the local community should receive collective rights from the producers, thus, GI protection can be given to areas that produce natural resources that can create economic value products and compete. Thus, the local community jointly protect natural resources that have the potential to provide royalties to them. This can further optimize the protection of GIs and provide more social justice to local communities. Collective rights to brand rights need to be considered to use the area name on the logo or brand name.

Conclusion

Favorable legal provisions governing Geographical Indications as the implementation of international provisions (especially TRIPs) have not been fully able to provide certainty and optimal benefits in protecting national assets from being owned by the state. This legal provision has not yet provided optimal protection for areas that can produce superior products. GI in many regions in Indonesia has a high economic value so that it has the potential for local economic development. Because GI protection is not clear because it is associated with products that should be separated, the product owner is the Brand, not GI.

The unclear placement of GI protection in Indonesia has not been optimal in providing benefits and justice to local communities. Local communities should own the rights to areas that have economic value and can produce competitive products. The people in the region should have the potential to be given collective rights to receive royalties or profits from producers who take or market these superior products. The potential for granting collective rights to receive royalties will spur local communities to protect their natural resources or local assets actively and to take an active role in supporting the implementation of GI protection.

Clear GI protection will provide opportunities for local communities to participate in processing natural resources contained in their territory that have the potential to compete and gain equality to get business opportunities and profits.

References

- Alexy, R. (2006) *Gustav Radbruch 's Concept of Law*. Cam: Harvard University Press.
- Arinanto, S. and Triyanti, N. (2012) *Memahami Hukum : Dari konstruksi sampai implementasi*. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
- Mayasari, D. E. (2020) 'Protection of Geographical Indications as a Form of Consumer Rights Protection', *Yuridika*, 35(1), pp. 41–54. doi: 10.20473/ydk.v35i1.13990.
- Montrn, L. (2006) 'Geographical Indications of Origin: Should They Be Protected and Why?', *Santa Clara High Technology Law Journal*, 22(2), pp. 315–349.
- Panel Reports, E. (2020) 'Protection of Geographical Indications', *The EC Regulation*. Australia, pp. 202–213.
- Pitegoff, P. R. (2017) 'Community Development Law, Economic Justice, and the Legal Academy', *Journal of Affordable Housin*, 26(1), pp. 31–75. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234112205.pdf>.
- Rahardjo, S. (2003) *Sisi-sisi lain dari hukum di Indonesia*. Jakarta: Kompas.
- Roberts, M. J. and Reich, M. R. (2011) *Pharmaceutical Reform: A Guide to Improving Performance and Equity*, *Pharmaceutical Reform*. Washington DC: The Word Bank. doi: 10.1596/978-0-8213-8760-3.
- Salim, H. and Nurbaini, E. S. (2013) *Penerapan Teori Hukum pada Penelitian Disertasi dan Tesis*. Jakarta: Rajawali Pers.
- Sarac, J. (2015) *The role of the agreement on Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) in the system intellectual property protection*, *International Journal Vallis Aurea*. doi: 10.2507/ijva.1.2.9.21.
- Sitepu, F. Y. (2018) 'The potential of geographical indications and Its legal protection', *E3S Web of Conferences*, 52, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1051/e3sconf/20185200017.
- Sutrisno, E. (2014) 'Implementasi Pengelolaan Sumber Daya Pesisir Berbasis Pengelolaan Wilayah Pesisir Secara Terpadu Untuk Kesejahteraan Nelayan', *Jurnal Dinamika Hukum*, 14(1), pp. 1–12. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234650142.pdf>.
- Sutrisno, E. (2015) 'Tracing the Performance of Law in Indonesia', *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization*, 37, pp. 126–137. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/234650142.pdf>.
- Sutrisno, E. (2019) 'Relations between legal culture and economic empowerment among marginalized group of farmers', *Journal of Legal, Ethical and Regulatory Issues*, 22(3), pp. 1–9. Available at: <https://www.abacademies.org/articles/Relations-between-legal-culture-and-economic-empowerment-among-marginalized-group-of-Farmers-1544-0044-22-3-329.pdf>.
- Warassih, E. (2011) 'Pranata hukum', *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling*. Semarang: Universitas Diponogora, pp. 1689–1699.

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